

GLOBAL DISTRIBUTIONS AND MORPHOMETRIC COMPARISON OF "SINUOUS RILLES" ON THE MOON AND VENUS. D. Defilippis¹ and G. Komatsu¹, ¹ International Research School of Planetary Sciences, Università d'Annunzio, Viale Pindaro 42, 65127 Pescara, Italy (davide.defilippis@studenti.unich.it).

Introduction: Sinuous rilles (SRs) are considered to have formed by massive quantities of lava flowing on planetary surfaces, which involved thermomechanical erosion. They have diverse morphologies such as source depressions, tortuous paths and/or more linear ones narrowing and shallowing distally. They can have depth and width ranges reaching from hundreds of meters to kilometers and length up to hundreds of kilometers, much greater in size compared to typical lava channels observed on terrestrial lava fields. Based the Kaguya SELENE Orbiter (2007) data with the resolution up to 10 m/px and a global coverage, an update of the lunar SRs catalog was made [1] over the earlier effort [2], reaching a total of 194 SRs. For Venus, the Magellan mission (1989) reported some channels with a width range of about 1 km [3], emanating from large pits similar to lunar SRs. Global mapping [4, 5, 6] reported more than 200 cases of venusian channels and valleys, recognizing common morphological characteristics classified as four distinct types: simple, complex, compound and integrated. Among the simple ones, there are 59 identified venusian SRs. We produced new global distribution maps of lunar and venusian SRs and also performed their morphometric analysis building on earlier studies [7, 8]. Our new observations through data provided by three spacecraft probes, the Lunar Reconnaissance Orbiter (LRO) and Kaguya for the Moon and Magellan for Venus, led to the detection of 264 lunar SRs (compared with previously known 194 SRs) and 372 SRs on Venus (compared with previously known 60 SRs), greatly improving the existing catalogs and providing implications on their global distributions. Then, measurements of diverse parameters such as length, distance, sinuosity index, width and depth were made in order to identify potential morphological trends.

Formation process of sinuous rilles: The formation mechanisms hypothesized are mainly three: 1. gradual cooling of lava, which allows the construction of a channel with levees above the surroundings [9, 10]; 2. mechanical erosion by lava incising the substrate [11]; 3. thermal erosion due to thermal difference between lava and substrate [12–21]. In reality, a combination of the three mechanisms can be more plausible [e.g., 17], because depending on the degree of consolidation and the inclination of substrate, either one process or the other may prevail, e.g., if substrate is very solid and inclination is low, the construction of levees prevails. If inclination is high

enough, mechanical erosion predominates, but if the substrate is poorly consolidated with a low inclination, thermal erosion prevails. The different formation processes may produce various depth trends along the channel: if the depth decreases with increasing distance from the source, the prevailing mechanism can be indicated as thermal erosion, while if the depth of the channel is irregular, the dominant process can be mechanical erosion [12, 20, 21].

Methodology: *Data:* For the Moon, the base map is the mosaic from WAC of LRO [22]. The mosaic is implemented with an equirectangular centric projection central longitude at 0°, with spatial resolution of 100 m/px, added to this are TC images from Kaguya, with a spatial resolution of about 8 m/px [23]. Then, to better highlight the rilles, a selection of TC rasters with lighting from West (TC morning) and from East (TC evening) are introduced. Elevation is derived from the DEM, based on data from LOLA on board the LRO, with a spatial resolution of 118 m/px and global coverage [24]. On Venus, the base map is the mosaic produced by the Full resolution Basic Image Data Records (F-BIDRs) from the Magellan SAR (left-look) [25], implemented with an equirectangular centric projection central longitude at 0°. Elevation is obtained from the merged SAR stereoscopic data with Magellan's Altimeter and Radiometry Composite Data Record (ARCDR) data, resulting in a raster with spatial resolution of 600 m/px and a vertical resolution of approximately 100 m, but with a partial global coverage of about 20% of the surface [26].

Measurements: A total of 690 channels are identified (264 lunar SRs, 372 venusian SRs, 54 canali are identified for comparison to SRs for Venus) and mapped with linear features following the thalweg. In this way, it is possible to measure the precise length and distance from the starting point/source to terminal part. Then, sinuosity index (SI) is calculated through length/distance ratio, distinguishing them into different classes (SI<1.05 almost straight, 1.05<SI<1.25 winding, 1.25<SI<1.50 twisty, SI>1.50 meandering). In order to measure width and depth of SRs, it was necessary to produce sections perpendicular to thalwegs, resulting in an average measurement for SRs without source; while only for SRs with a source, further perpendicular sections were made to evaluate width and depth also at the beginning and end of flow.

Figure 1. Distributions of SRs on Moon (above) and Venus (red) with canali (yellow) (below)

Results: Distribution: On the Moon, the greatest concentration of SRs (42%) is found in the Oceanus Procellarum region (Fig. 1) near the margins between maria and terrae, owing to the presence of areas affected by the outpouring of basaltic lavas. Oceanus Procellarum KREEP Terrane lavas were composed of magmas highly enriched in incompatible and heat-producing elements preserved from the magmatic oceanic period, which may have remained partially molten for several hundred million years, producing SRs. On Venus, a high SRs concentration is found in the Seoritsu Farra area, (45%) (Fig. 1) linked to the presence of numerous coronae probably formed by the interaction of plumes/surface. SRs are mainly located near coronae, montes, tholi, fluctus, chasmata, paterae and in areas affected by deformation and volcanism as reported earlier [5, 6].

Distance/Length: lunar SRs stretch on the order of tens of km, and venusian SRs can reach hundreds of km. Comparatively, lunar SRs cover shorter distances and greater lengths, while SRs on Venus cover greater distances and shorter lengths, determining different sinuous morphologies. Sinuosity index: between 1.05 and 1.25 (winding) are the most numerous for both lunar and venusian SRs; for >1.50 (meandering), lunar SRs are more numerous than venusian ones.

Width/Length: venusian SRs are concentrated for low ratios, characterized by greater length with smaller channel width than lunar SRs which have greater width for the same length.

Width/Depth: lunar SRs are noted for lower ratios than venusian ones, having greater depth at the same width than those on Venus, which are shallower.

Width/Depth at the source and the end of SRs follow the same trend as the average results (398 out of 690 channels have an observable source: 119/264 lunar SRs Moon; 262/372 venusian SRs).

Discussion and Conclusion: In conclusion, the distribution of SRs on the two planetary surfaces is not random but strongly depends on the geology and history of the planetary bodies. Venusian SRs have greater length and distance than lunar SRs. However, at the same distance lunar SRs are longer than venusian ones and this translates to a greater sinuosity. Furthermore, lunar SRs have greater width than venusian SRs at the equal length; while for depth, lunar SRs have greater average depth than venusian SRs with the same average width. The same trend is observed at the source and terminus of the channels, keeping the ratio between width and depth constant. The above observations are possibly related to the combination of mechanical and thermal erosion acted more efficiently to form tortuous channels for lunar SRs rather than making them reach long distances. Such differences may arise from the involved magmas (i.e., KREEP or plume-related underneath coronae).

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